

The Model of Modulus Degradation near Edges Zones for Composite Materials

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The entropy model of the damage accumulation for static and dynamic loading of composite structures is developed. New method of calculation of the effective stiffness characteristics for composite structures made from in-homogeneous composite materials is offered.

The other types structures of composite materials and discontinuities connected with various sorts of microdefects are considered. The method of effective parameters calculations based on the using of some system relations which follow from variational consideration in result of expansion of the system of varied parameters and obtaining of appropriate factor in their isoperimetrical relations. These relations is proposed to use for definition of the effective parameters of the in-homogeneous composite medium, composite beams, shells and plates with set of the dispersed microdefects. The variants of the entropy and micromechanic models are applied to description of the damage accumulation which allow to take into account both processes: appearance and growth process of microdefects. The other types of the defects that may control of the unidirectional composite damage are considered (break down of filaments, matrix delamination from broken fibers, transversal microcracks in matrix and so on). The accumulation damage models further are used in calculation of the effective characteristics of the composite structures. It is represented essential, that the proposed method allow to take into account the stress distributions and to receive an evaluation of accuracy of the calculated characteristics associated with using approximate solutions of the stress state. As examples the effective elastic constants of the two-phase medium, generalized stiffness, bending rigidities of the plates and shells taking into account refined theories and damage accumulation are founded.